

Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Indium (III) Complexes with Thiosalicylic, Salicylic and Anthranilic Acid

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The complexes of indium(III) with thiosalicylic acid, salicylic acid and anthranilic acid have been investigated by the potentiometric titration technique in 75% v/v aqueous ethanol media in the presence of 0.2 M sodium perchlorate. The proton-ligand stability constants and the stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti. The log K values have been computed by the alternative methods. The values of stepwise and overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the complex formation reactions have also been evaluated at 30° by carrying out the experiments at 20°, 30° and 40°. The trend in the stability constant values of indium(III) complexes has been found to be thiosalicylic > anthranilic > salicylic acid.

IN our earlier communications^{1,2} we have reported the stepwise formation constants and the thermodynamic parameters for the complexes of indium(III) with mercapto, hydroxy and amino substituted analogs of succinic and propionic acid. We now present in this paper for the first time the results obtained with benzoic acid derivatives.

The stepwise formation constants of In(III) complexes and the proton-ligand stability constants of thiosalicylic acid (TSA), salicylic acid (SA) and anthranilic acid (AA) have been obtained at three different temperatures. The free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) accompanying the complex forming reactions have also been evaluated.

Experimental

Materials: The stock solutions of the ligands were prepared in ethanol using thiosalicylic acid, anthranilic acid and salicylic acid (B.D.H.) and were standardised by potentiometric titration in 75% v/v aqueous ethanol media. The metal solution was prepared from 99.9% pure indium nitrate pentahydrate and indium content was estimated by precipitation as 8-hydroxyquinolate³. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.0 M) was prepared by a standard technique⁴ using a AnalaR sample of E. Merck and was standardised potentiometrically against potassium hydrogen phthalate. The stock solution of sodium perchlorate (neutral) and perchloric acid was prepared by dissolving AnalaR sample of NaClO₄·H₂O (Riedel) and HClO₄ (E. Merck). The concentration of perchloric acid was determined by titrating it potentiometrically against sodium hydroxide.

Apparatus: A pH-meter (Beckmann model H-2) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to

determine the change in hydrogen ion concentration of the solution. The saturated calomel electrode was connected to the cell externally by means of an agar bridge, saturated with KNO₃ to prevent the formation of chloro complexes. The pH-indicator scale was calibrated with aqueous buffers and in the calculation of free ligand concentration the pH-meter readings were directly used. The use of the pH meter readings instead of true pH values do not involve any error^{5,6} in the calculation of free ligand concentration. The design of the cell was such that it allowed nitrogen (presaturated with solvent) to be passed through the solution and enabled measurements to be carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an electrically maintained thermostat having a regulating accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometries of the reactions between In (III) and TSA, SA and AA were determined by potentiometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard sodium hydroxide (1.0 M). The following four mixtures in 75% v/v aqueous ethanol media were prepared: A: $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand; B: $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution; C: $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution and D: $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $1.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution. A graph of pH meter reading (B) vs. moles of NaOH per mole of ligand (m) was plotted.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants: In order to calculate these constants, the Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique^{7,8} was employed. Three titrations were carried out (a) perchloric acid at a concentration of EM (E = 0.01 for TSA and SA; E = 0.02 for AA) was titrated against NM sodium hydroxide (N = 1.0), (b) perchloric acid (concentration = EM) plus ligand (concentration = T_L' about

0.005M) was titrated against NM sodium hydroxide; and (c) perchloric acid (concentration = EM) plus ligand (concentration = T_L) and metal (concentration = T_M where $T_M = 1/5 T_L$ for TSA and $1/3 T_L$ for SA and AA) was titrated against NM sodium hydroxide. In all these titration 75% v/v aqueous ethanol media was maintained.

The initial volume of the titration solution in each case was V^0 ; volumes V' , V'' and V''' of alkali were consumed in titrations (a), (b) and (c) respectively to give identical pH meter reading (B).

A ligand-proton formation curve was then obtained by plotting the degree of formation (\bar{n}_A) of the ligand-proton complex against B , using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti⁵.

$$\bar{n}_A = Y + [(V' - V'') / (V^0 + V')] [(N + E) / T_L] \quad \dots (1)$$

where Y is the total number of replaceable protons per ligand molecule added at the beginning of the titration.

A complex-ligand formation curve was then obtained by plotting the degree of formation of the complex (\bar{n}) against the negative logarithm of the concentration of the non-protonated ligand (pL), using the following two relationships⁵

$$\bar{n} = (V''' - V'') [N + E + T_L (Y - \bar{n}_A)] / (V^0 + V'') \times \bar{n}_A T_M \quad \dots (2)$$

$$pL = \log \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} P \beta_n H (1/\text{antilog } B)^n}{(T_L - \bar{n} T_M)} \cdot \frac{(V^0 + V''')}{V^0} \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

The 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants were determined from the formation curves using two methods⁹—(a) interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values, and (b) interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values. Whereas for the metal-ligand stability constants four different methods⁹ were applied to the formation curves (a) interpolation at half n values, (b) interpolation at various \bar{n} values, (c) correction term method, (d) least squares method.

Thermodynamic Parameters : Values of the overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complex formation have been calculated using the temperature co-efficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation¹⁰. The various relationships employed are :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad \dots (4)$$

$$d \log K / d(1/T) = \Delta H / 4.57 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G) / T \quad \dots (6)$$

Results

Stoichiometry : In establishing the stoichiometries of the complex species with TSA, the appearance of an inflection (Fig. 1, curve A) after the addition of one mole of base per mole of the ligand corresponds to the complete neutralisation of the single carboxyl hydrogen. Hence if free TSA, having two replaceable

hydrogen ions is denoted as H_2TSA , the reaction between 'm' interval of 0-1 may be represented by the equation (7)

Another inflection at $m \approx 2$ (Fig. 1, curve A) shows that the second proton of TSA is titrable only in the alkaline range. Thus it is obvious that only two ligand species H_2TSA and $HTSA^-$ exist in the pH range corresponding to the values of m from 0 to 1. Addition of an equimolar concentration of In(III) ions (Fig. 1, curve B) greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of complex formation and consequently a considerable shift in the position of the end point is indicated. The large fall in the initial pH value and the lowered

Fig. 1. Stoichiometry of In(III)-TSA complex :
 Concentration of titrant = 1.0M NaOH
 Concentration of TSA = 5.0×10^{-3} M
 Concentration of In(III) : Curve A—0.0;
 Curve B— 5.0×10^{-3} M; Curve C— 2.5×10^{-3} M;
 Curve D— 1.66×10^{-3} M.

buffer region between 'm' = 0-2 clearly shows the displacement of proton from the -SH group, due to complexation, since the extent of proton displacement depends upon the relative affinities of the ligand for hydrogen ions. It is obvious from the curve that the interaction of In (III) with TSA is sufficiently great and the metal ion can compete with hydrogen ion for the ligand even at relatively low pH, and hence a considerable lowering in the buffer region starts. But the stoichiometry cannot be concluded from this titration since precipitation occurred before any inflection appeared (Fig. 1, curve B).

The titration of In(III) in the presence of two moles of TSA (Fig. 1, Curve C) shows an inflection at $m \approx 2$ indicating the formation of $\text{In}(\text{TSA})_2^-$. The reaction equilibria may be expressed by the equation (8). However, the titration could not be continued

in the alkaline range as precipitation occurred at about pH 7, due to the hydrolysis of the complex species (Fig. 1, curve C).

By titrating a mixture containing 1 : 3 ratio of In(III) to TSA (Fig. 1, curve D), the curve shows only one inflection at $m \approx 2$ indicating the formation of $\text{In}(\text{TSA})_3^{3-}$. The reaction equilibria may be expressed by equation (9)

In establishing the stoichiometries of the complex species formed by AA with In(III), in all the titrations a constant amount of strong acid was added to bring down the pH. It was observed that below the pH value of hydrolysis of free metal ion, considerable lowering occurred in the free ligand titration curve when mixtures, containing metal ion were titrated. Thus it may be concluded that $-\text{COOH}$ as well as $-\text{NH}_2$ group which has very less proton affinity in this case, as discussed in the latter part, are deprotonated during complexation. However no inflection was observed at any ratio before precipitation occurred; this shows that although the complexation is rather strong, but it is not sufficient to mask the most common reaction of indium ion i.e., the precipitation of $\text{In}(\text{OH})_3$. The precipitation began at about pH 3.6 from non-complex solution but in the presence of AA it is shifted to pH 4.6.

Finally, in the titrations of In(III)-SA system, the precipitation of In(III) at pH 3.8, slight lowering in the pH value and the absence of inflection before precipitation took place shows that no proton is liberated during complexation from the phenolic OH group.

Proton-ligand stability constants : The formation curves were extended between 0 to 2 for TSA and AA and 0 to 1 for SA in \bar{n}_A scale indicating dissociation of H_2TSA , H_2AA^+ and HSA as follows :

The mean values of $\log {}^P K_1^H$ and $\log {}^P K_2^H$ at various temperatures for all the ligands obtained by applying different methods to the formation curves have been summarised in Table 1, and they have the error limits of ± 0.03 .

TABLE 1—STEPWISE PROTON—LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES AND $\mu = 0.2M$

Ligand	Constants*	$t = 20^\circ$	$t = 30^\circ$	$t = 40^\circ$
TSA	$\log {}^P K_1^H$	9.11	9.00	8.90
	$\log {}^P K_2^H$	4.11	4.13	4.14
	$\log P\beta^H$	13.22	13.13	13.04
AA	$\log {}^P K_1^H$	5.12	5.06	5.01
	$\log {}^P K_2^H$	1.96	1.98	1.99
	$\log P\beta^H$	7.08	7.04	7.00
SA	$\log {}^P K_1^H$	3.09	3.12	3.14
	* ± 0.03			

Metal-ligand stability constants : In(III)-TSA : The formation curves are extended between the values of $\bar{n} = 0$ to 3 (Fig. 2). The existence of three step equilibria is thus indicated. Moreover the curve flattens at $\bar{n} = 3$ showing the formation of maximum three complexes. The mean values of stepwise stability constants obtained by the various computational methods at various temperatures have been summarised in Table 2. The error limits are ± 0.03 for $\log K_1$ and ± 0.05 for $\log K_2$ and K_3 values of the stability constants.

In(III)-AA and In(III)-SA : In both these cases the metal curves did not join up parallel with the ligand curves indicating liberation of extra protons due to hydrolysis of metal ions. Hence only the lower pH regions of the titrations curves were used for calculation in order to preclude errors due to hydrolysis. The mean values of $\log K_1$ for AA obtained by method (a) and (b) and $\log K_2$ by method (d) from the formation curves (Fig. 3) at different temperatures have been summarised in Table 2. For SA only $\log K_1$ values obtained by method (a) from formation curves (Fig. 4) at various temperatures have been reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STEPWISE METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF INDIUM(III) COMPLEXES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES AND $\mu = 0.2M$

Complex	Constants	$t = 20^\circ$	$t = 30^\circ$	$t = 40^\circ$
In(III)-TSA	$\log K_1^*$	11.16	11.10	11.05
	$\log K_2^@$	9.02	8.90	8.80
	$\log K_3^@$	6.11	5.96	5.79
	$\log \beta$	26.29	25.96	25.64
In(III)-AA	$\log K_1^*$	5.29	5.24	5.20
	$\log K_2^@$	4.34	4.27	4.19
	$\log \beta$	9.63	9.51	9.39
In(III)-SAA	$\log K_1^*$	2.54	2.59	2.65

* ± 0.03 ; @ ± 0.05 .

Thermodynamic parameters : The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and

Fig. 2. Formation curves of In(III)-SA complex at $t = 20^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 40° ; $\mu = 0.2$.

Fig. 3. Formation curves of In(III)-AA complex at $t = 20^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 40° ; $\mu = 0.2$.

entropy (ΔS) accompanying the metal-ligand complex forming reactions have been calculated at 30° , $\mu = 0.2$ and are summarised in Table 3. The precision of ΔH values is ± 0.5 Kcal/mole for first step and ± 1.0 Kcal/mole for the second and third steps.

Fig. 4. Formation curves of In(III)-TSA complex at $t = 20^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 40° ; $\mu = 0.2$.

The precision of ΔS values is ± 2.0 cal/deg/mole for the first step and ± 3 cal/deg/mole for the higher steps.

Discussion

From the experimental data it is clear that TSA forms strongest complexes with indium(III). This can be attributed to the fact that $-SH$ group acts as the strongest complexing group, as reported earlier by us^{1,2} for similar types of ligands. In the present case it is seen that $-OH$ group substituted ligand (SA) forms the least stable complexes and the complexes formed by the NH_2 group substituted ligand (AA) has greater stability. This increasing tendency for NH_2 against $-OH$ has been found to be different from that reported earlier by us for the ligands containing aliphatic organic residue^{1,2}. For these ligands it was observed that the stability of the complexes decreased as the substituted group was changed from $-OH$ to NH_2 . This difference in the present case can be explained due to the occurrence of mesomeric effect in AA as shown below :

Due to this effect the pK value of $-COOH$ group increases and the proton affinity of NH_2 group decreases. Thus it will cause a increase in the metal-ligand formation constant. It has been commonly observed that as the pK value of the $-COOH$ group increases the stability constant of the metal-ligand also increases. The very high stability of $-SH$ group containing ligand (TSA) can be explained in terms of $M \rightarrow L, \pi$ bond in addition to

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF In(III) COMPLEXES AT 30°

Parameters	In(III)-TSA	In(III)-AA	In(III)-SA
ΔG_1 KCal/mole	-15.39 ± 0.05	-7.26 ± 0.05	-3.59 ± 0.05
ΔG_2 Kcal/mole	-12.34 ± 0.08	-5.92 ± 0.08	—
ΔG_3 Kcal/mole	-8.26 ± 0.08	—	—
ΔH_1 Kcal/mole	-2.3 ± 0.5	-1.9 ± 0.5	$+2.1 \pm 0.5$
ΔH_2 Kcal/mole	-4.6 ± 1.0	-3.2 ± 1.0	—
ΔH_3 Kcal/mole	-6.8 ± 1.0	—	—
ΔS_1 cal/deg/mole	$+43 \pm 2$	$+17 \pm 2$	$+19 \pm 2$
ΔS_2 cal/deg/mole	$+25 \pm 3$	$+9 \pm 3$	—
ΔS_3 cal/deg/mole	$+5 \pm 3$	—	—

M → L, σ bond, since indium (III) has d^{10} configuration and that vacant $d\pi$ orbitals are available on the sulfur atom for the π interactions¹¹.

The large increase in entropy values for the first step can be explained due to the charge neutralisation involving trivalent indium ion which has a great ordering effect on the solvent. Similar results have been reported for Fe^{3+} complexes by Aditya *et al.*¹². The smaller positive values of entropy for the subsequent complexes show that there is decreasing importance of the disruption of the hydration sphere surrounding the cations. This decrease in the disruption of hydration shepere can be explained, due to the placement of the anions immediately adjacent to the cation, as well as due to the decrease in the net charge attracting the hydration sphere. Thus it would seem reasonable to conclude that the greater stability for the first step complexation is largely by entropy contribution and the consecutive steps by both, enthalpy as well as entropy. It is also seen that ΔH values for In(III)-TSA complexes are exothermic which supports the In-S, π interactions. For In(III)-AA complexes the values are slightly exothermic which show that the bonds formed are relatively weaker or the complex may be having salt like nature. The values of ΔH for In(III)-SA complexes are endothermic which shows that the complex species are formed by the electrostatic interactions and they are stabilised only by the large positive entropy changes due to the liberation of water molecules from the ions accompanying complex formation. Lastly, the comparison of stability constants of In(III)-TSA complexes with those reported for In(III)-mercaptopropionate in our earlier communication show that the six-membered aliphatic ring binds indium ions less effectively than a six-membered ring through the benzene ring.

This situation is analogous to that reported by Schwarzenbach^{13,14}.

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